

Computation for the Summation of Integers and Geometric Progression of Powers of Two

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Abstract: Geometric series plays a vital role in the areas of combinatorics, science, economics, and medicine. This paper presents computing technique for the sum of positive integers and geometric series whose terms are powers of two. This computing technique is a methodological advance which is useful for researchers who are working in science, economics, engineering, computation, and management.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series. The geometric series and its summations and sums [1-9] have significant applications in science, engineering, economics, queuing theory, computation, management, and medicine [10]. In this article, an innovative idea is introduced for the computation of sum of positive integers and geometric series whose terms are powers of two.

2. Computation of Geometric Series

Theorem: $\sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1} = (n-1)2^n + 1$.

Proof. This theorem is proved by mathematical induction.

Basis. Let $n = 3$. Then $\sum_{i=1}^3 i \times 2^{i-1} = 1 + 4 + 12 = 17 = 2 \times 2^3 + 1$. It is true.

Inductive hypothesis. Let us assume that it is true for $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} i \times 2^{i-1} = (n-2)2^{n-1} + 1$.

Inductive Step. We must show that $\sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1} = (n-1)2^n + 1$ is true.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} i \times 2^{i-1} + n2^{n-1} = (n-2)2^{n-1} + 1 + n2^{n-1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1} = 2n2^{n-1} - 22^{n-1} + 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1} = n2^n - 2^n + 1 = (n-1)2^n + 1.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, an innovative idea is introduced a computational technique for the computation of sum of positive integers and geometric series whose terms are powers of two. This computing technique is a methodological advance which is useful for researchers who are working in science, economics, engineering, computation, and management.

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